

THE IMPORTANCE OF JOKES IN ENGLISH NOVELS

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ANNOTATION. The article analyzes the place of English jokes in daily communication, in various mass media, in the works of famous English writers from a linguocultural point of view.

KEY WORDS. Jokes, humour, culture, misunderstanding, English dialogues, tradition, british films

ANNOTATSIYA. Maqola ingliz hazillarining kundalik muloqotda, turli ommaviy axborot vositalarida, mashxur ingliz yozuvchilarning asarlarida tutgan o'rninin lingvomadaniy jihatdan taxlil qiladi

Kalit SO‘ZLAR. Hazillar, yumor, madaniyat, tushunmovchilik, inglizcha dialoglar, an'analar, ingliz filmlari

Despite the fact that the English language, which is widely spread around the world, is constantly being analyzed and researched by linguists in various fields, there are still many unexplored aspects of it. There are not only phonetic or grammatical differences between English and Uzbek, but cultural differences directly affect the conversation process.

No matter what nationality the jokes belong to, they all have a truth hidden beneath the laughter. People hide their problems in different words. Philologists have described humor as "tears that the world does not move", that is, greatness behind weakness, wisdom behind madness, sadness behind laughter. According to some parables, joy and sorrow meet in the forest and marry without knowing each other. A child named joke is born from them. The essence of this parable also shows that there is seriousness behind the joke.

Humor is multifaceted, and it is broadly understood as a mixed approach of indiscriminate laughter to a certain phenomenon of life. In the narrow sense, funny situations and jokes are understood as a result of a person expressing his personality in various unusual or metaphorical ways. The first category includes various works of art, examples of creativity, and the second includes all kinds of jokes.

Humor is a limitless topic for conversations and even debates. Whoever's humor is natural, deep and innocent, not only the people of that region, but also other peoples and countries will become fans of it. It's no secret that English jokes cause a lot of controversy. It is worth saying that English jokes are distinguished from other nations' jokes by their naturalness. In Great Britain there is an expression:

“Everyone has a fool in his sleeve”

There are enough "word beats" in English dialogues. They are affected by each other's words and gestures in communication processes and respond [5,26].

British jokes, like those of other nations, are not without diversity. The stupidest jokes are called elephant jokes. There are also jokes that are part of the "banana skin sense of humor". An example of this type of humor is an Englishman who runs after a bus for a long time and when the bus doors are opened, he falls with his whole body on an old woman's dirty shoes. Is it funny? Although this situation does not call for laughter in our nation, the British welcome it with laughter [4,150].

As mentioned above, understanding English words is problematic. To solve this, it is necessary to study their culture, lifestyle, profession, values, family environment and, of course, their character. For example, one of Britain's favorite topics of conversation is the weather. In Europe, it is hardly mentioned. Even when talking about a completely different topic, the British often throw in humorous sentences about the weather.

John Lennon, who is known and famous all over the world, made jokes about many subjects. He was able to make jokes about almost everything and whoever the audience was. His dark humor has gained fans not only in Britain, but also abroad. Anyone interested in Lennon's life and career will not find it difficult to notice his love of cats. Her eloquence and wit can also be seen in the naming of her cats. Major and Minor [4,144] .

In England, there is such a tradition, according to which "Red Nose" day is celebrated every two years in the spring season. This charity event is dedicated to orphans and disabled children. At the so-called "Comic Festival", "red noses" are sold in advance, people dress up in funny clothes, make different crazy hairstyles, mask their faces with different colors and stick red noses. People donate their money by buying red noses, artists participate in their shows, athletes participate in various exercises, and by donating. All this attracts investment. This charity is held all over England and various competitions are organized. In the evening, all the collected money will be calculated. The collected funds are sent to Africa, Asia, America, Russia and other similar countries to support, provide food and education to children in need.

The BBC broadcasts all-night events, watch shows, sports performances, and details of how serious the cause is behind it and where the money goes.

Among the English jokes, one can also find one related to the river Thames. But this is a joke that has already grown old.

"London. An English gentleman's room. The door opened and a servant came in:

- Flood!
- Go out and explain again.

The servant came out and closed the door behind him, after a while he opened the door again and said:

"Thames, sir."

We look at English literature and movies. For a more complete account of English humor, see Jerome K. Consider Jerome's *Three Men in a Boat*, a unique example of English humor. In it, the author expresses the situation of the heroes of the work in a funny way. The comic nature of strange misunderstandings and incidents reflects the British psyche. At first glance, everything seems to be exaggerated, a half-smile appears on the face, but after a while, when a person remembers such events in his life, for example, during the process of renovating the house, trying to heal himself, or when he remembers his actions in similar life situations, he bursts out laughing. laughing is natural. Jerome K. Jerome was a writer who could make a laugh out of such ordinary situations. His jokes are sincere, and his characters, despite all their ineptitude, evoke a friendly mood in readers. Anyone who has read this piece will surely remember the scenes of the characters trying to open the lid of the pineapple jar, George trying to play the banjo, and Harris singing [2,276].

British films are an important factor in the global recognition of English humor. There is probably no one who does not know Sherlock Holmes and Dr. Watson. Almost every sentence in this movie is a joke. In particular, the phrase "cereal, sir" became famous not only in Britain, but also in other countries. It is interesting that Arthur Conan Doyle uses this phrase in his works less than screenwriters. In England and Scotland, porridge made from semolina is a common morning meal, and the phrase is now used for every intolerable occasion. For example, it can also be applied to incessant rains in the country [3,13].

"For two weeks this cereal has been bothering me."

Or the words of the student before the sessions:

"Oh, our favorite oatmeal again"

There is a national joke in the jokes. English humor is considered to be more refined and aristocratic. According to researchers, English jokes have their

own characteristics that go back to their long history. They can take even the most ridiculous situations seriously. An example of such a feature is Shakespeare, Byron, Thackeray, Oscar Wilde, Jerome K. We can take the works of Jerome and others.

According to the results of the research, jokes are one of the manifestations of the culture of the British nation. For them, joking is as natural as breathing. they can laugh at themselves and others with great skill. This trait is a centuries-old idea in England that a person should be inculcated with the ability to joke. Otherwise it will not be perfect.

Humor haunts the British everywhere: in the mirror of the world, in radio broadcasts, in books and various publications, as well as in everyday life. English speakers are not affected by such jokes because they have become a part of English life. But for representatives of other nationalities, it may be more difficult to understand them, to understand their essence. In our opinion, no nation has the ability to laugh at itself like the English. For them, the subject of humor knows no bounds. They can laugh at everything in sight. Even over things that have been held sacred for years.

The pinnacle of English humor lies in the ability to laugh at one's own shortcomings in difficult situations. In such situations, it is important for them not to be offended by a joke, but to be able to understand such a joke and respond appropriately to it. English people joke about their seriousness of feelings, slowness of actions, mistakes and even bad luck.

The spread of the English language also spread to the world the unique jokes of the people who are the owners of this language. This helped to understand the culture and mentality of the British people. However, these jokes are not appreciated by other nations who have different cultures. As serious as the English people are, their humorous outlook on life is remarkably high. The German writer Jan Paul writes about this: "Serious people have a strong and

impressive passion for humor" [1, 448].

The English nation, judging from his serious appearance, considers it an insult to be suspected of not understanding a joke. For the English nation, the power of humor is not significant, because it has become their way of life. But for representatives of other nationalities, it can be difficult to understand them, to understand their essence. The pinnacle of English humor lies in the ability to laugh at one's own shortcomings in difficult situations. In such a situation, it is very important not to be offended by a joke, but to approach it positively and respond appropriately.

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